

Privilege in publishing: Investigating the impact of scientific reputation on peer review outcomes.

Rebecca Marjoram*, Geoff Krause** and Philippe Mongeon**

*rmarjoram@dal.ca

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7438-6258>

Department of Information Science, Dalhousie University, Canada

**gkrause@dal.ca; **pmongeon@dal.ca

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7943-5119>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1021-059X>

Department of Information Science, Dalhousie University, Canada

1. Introduction and Background

Scholarly journals are a main avenue of knowledge dissemination for academic research. The journal system provides quality control through peer-review and are where scholarly communities develop and discourses emerge. They are also spaces where the reputations of authors are built. Previous research has shown that biases exist in the journal system: the gender and ethnicities of researchers still play a role in the likelihood of a researcher being included as an author on a publication and in having their work cited (Larivière et al., 2013; Nielsen & Andersen, 2021; Rossiter, 1993). If underrepresented groups are less likely to be cited or included as authors on publications, they have fewer opportunities to build social capital within their field (i.e. fewer citations, fewer publications, fewer years since first publication). Underrepresented groups lend diversity to science which in turn should prompt innovation, but if innovative connections are considered outside the scope of a journal, it is possible that this work is less likely to be published. Conversely, if an author with a strong reputation and high social capital attempts to publish work outside of journal scope, there may be leniencies which allow the work to be published: the authors with greater social capital can leverage this to drive discourse. If an author has less social capital, they may need to fit scope more closely in order to be published. This bias, if it exists, could stifle innovation and enforce academic conformity.

This work-in-progress seeks to evaluate the impact of the past performance of researchers have on their need to fit the scope of a journal to be published. Our hypothesis is that the publications of established researchers with strong research records will be less likely to fit the scope of the journal due to the Matthew Effect (Bothner et al., 2010; Kim & King, 2014; Merton, 1968; Piezunka et al., 2018), whereas researchers with less social capital will tend to publish papers that are more aligned with the scope of a journal. This preliminary analysis will evaluate authors who have published in the top 10 journals in Library and Information Science in the five-year period between 2019-2023, and using linear regression, determine if the number of citations and publications of these authors has an effect on the fit of their publications within the 10 selected journals.

Practical outcomes of this research include an increased awareness of the potential biases in peer-review and manuscript selection, which could help support the development of mitigating strategies at the policy or journal level.

2. Methods

Using the ScienceMetrix journal classification system (Archambault et al., 2011), the top 10 journals in the Library and Information Science (LIS) sub-field were selected for analysis

based on their 2022 CiteScore (CiteScore, 2023). The CiteScore is calculated as the average number of citations received in four calendar years to five peer-reviewed document types published in a journal in the same four years. This metric is published annually by Scopus. OpenAlex, a fully open and comprehensive database of scholarly works (Priem et al., 2022), was used to retrieve publication information, including journal ISSN, journal name, publication ID, publication title, abstract, number of citations, year of publication, and type of publication. This analysis only included peer-reviewed articles and did not include errata, letters, editorials, or paratext.

Author information was also retrieved from OpenAlex, including author ID, author name, number of works published by the author, and number of citations received by the author. In order to mitigate effects of author disambiguation issues within the data set, authors with more than 50,000 citations and more than 1200 publications were removed and not included in analysis.

Journal fit was determined by calculating the cosine similarity between an article and all other articles published in the same journal and five-year time frame. Journal fit is defined as the average similarity of a publication with all other publications within the same five-year period.

Linear regression analyses were conducted using number of publications and number of citations as independent variables and journal fit as the dependent variable. Regression modelling was done for each journal as well as all ten journals combined. Results were considered statistically significant if p-values for coefficients were less than 0.05.

3. Results

Table 1 shows the ten journals within the Library and Information Science sub-field used in the analysis, including journal CiteScore, number of articles published between 2019-2023 (inclusive), and the average cosine similarity score of each journal. A total of 4,152 articles were included in these analyses.

Table 1. Average similarity score of 10 LIS journals.

Journal	CiteScore	N articles	Avg. cosine similarity
Government Information Quarterly	17.3	384	0.129
Health Information and Libraries Journal	6.5	245	0.145
Information Processing and Management	14.8	1271	0.094
Information Retrieval Journal	5.9	33	0.149
Information and learning sciences	6.8	220	0.180
Journal of information Science	6.7	507	0.088
Journal of Informetrics	6.9	429	0.110
Journal of the Association for Information Science Technology	6.8	587	0.089
Online Information Review	5.4	408	0.130
The Bottom Line	6.7	68	0.160

Figure 1. Average cosine similarity score density for each journal.

Average cosine similarity scores for each article in each journal were plotted (Figure 1). Each journal shows an approximately normal distribution of scores upon visual inspection. Journals such as Information Processing and Management and Journal of Information Science had narrower ranges of values and greater kurtosis, indicating less diversity in content. Journals with less kurtosis and wider ranges in values such as Government Information Quarterly likely had greater diversity of content.

Of the authors retrieved from OpenAlex, 13,927 had publications in the ten selected journals within the 2019-2023 time frame. After removing extremely prolific authors (i.e. authors with more than 600 publications), the final data set included 10,137 authors. Figure 2 displays the distribution of the number of publications of each author who published in any of the ten journals. Figure 3 displays the distribution of the total number of citations received by each author who published in each of the ten journals. Both distributions have strong positive skewness.

Figure 2. Distribution of the total number of publications of authors published in each journal.

Figure 3. Distribution of the total number of citations of authors published in each journal.

Table 2 outlines the coefficient values for citations and publications in the linear regression model and adjusted R-squared values. Most coefficients were not statistically significant, and based on coefficient magnitude and adjusted R-squared values, those coefficients that were significant had negligible effect sizes.

Table 2. Coefficient estimates of number of publications and citations on average similarity.

Journal	Citations coefficient	Articles coefficient	Adjusted R-squared
Government Information Quarterly	0.000 (p = 0.900)	0.000 (p = 0.880)	-0.001
Health Information and Libraries Journal	-0.000 (p = 0.359)	-0.000 (p = 0.103)	0.007
Information Processing and Management	0.000 (p = 0.736)	0.000 (p = 0.572)	-0.000
Information Retrieval Journal	-0.000 (p = 0.044)*	0.000 (p = 0.276)	0.022
Information and learning sciences	0.000 (p = 0.351)	-0.000 (p = 0.276)	-0.001
Journal of Information Science	0.000 (p = 0.251)	-0.000 (p = 0.246)	-0.001
Journal of Informetrics	0.000 (p = 0.298)	-0.000 (p = 0.065)	0.001
Journal of the Association for Information Science Technology	-0.000 (p = 0.065)	-0.000 (p = 0.499)	0.005
Online Information Review	-0.000 (p = 0.286)	0.000 (p = 0.435)	-0.001
The Bottom Line	0.000 (p = 0.673)	-0.000 (p = 0.215)	-0.002
All journals model	0.000 (p = 0.012)*	-0.000 (p = 0.000)*	0.007

*indicates statistically significant p-value (p<0.05)

4. Discussion

Our preliminary findings do not offer strong support to the hypothesis that the more established a scholar is the more likely they are to publish articles that are less likely to fit the scope of the journal in which it is published. It is possible that while established researchers might be able to drive discourse through publishing innovative work, they may also be publishing works that are still closely related to current research trends. More exploration is necessary to determine if a relationship between scientific reputation metrics and article fit exists, including analysis of other scientific fields beyond LIS, and other factors such as academic age (number of years since authors' first publication) and sociodemographic factors including gender and ethnicity.

Another consideration is the rarity of peer-reviewed articles that fall outside of the scope of the journal – these publications are outliers, so the methods employed by this work-in-progress may not be sensitive enough to determine the factors that impact works published outside of scope. Future research could adjust this process by selecting outliers and analysing similarities between authors to determine if certain scientific reputation factors are over- or underrepresented.

Of note is the skewness of the number of publications and number of citations of the authors included in these analyses. Both metrics for all ten journals were strongly positively skewed, indicating that there a considerable number of authors with high publication and citation numbers, even after removing authors with excessive publications and citations that were likely caused by name disambiguation issues.

Methodologically, we considered number of publications and citations to be continuous, numeric variables in our analysis. This may not have been the best approach, as there may not be a material difference in an author having, for example, 30,000 versus 50,000 citations on the fit of their publications to a particular journal – the author would regardless be considered as having a strong reputation. Future development of this work will consider categorization of scientific reputation factors for models.

4.1 Limitations

This work evaluated a small set of journals from a singular sub-field within the academic publishing ecosystem. As such, it is possible that scientific reputation has little impact on journal fit within LIS but may be more pronounced in other sub-fields. Additionally, other factors that were not included in this analysis may have more of a role in authors needing to fit their work to match the scope of a journal.

This work was limited to published articles that included abstract text in English; it is possible that non-English publications or an analysis of full articles may elicit different results.

5. Conclusion

This work-in-progress is, to our knowledge, the first to evaluate authors' scientific reputation against how closely their publications fit within a journal. Using the top 10 journals in LIS based on CiteScore, we modelled the impact of number of citations and number of publications of the author on the fit of articles to a journal based on cosine similarity scores. Our hypothesis that the more publications and citations an author had made their publications less likely to fit the journals scope was not supported by our evaluation. Future research to evaluate more scientific sub-fields and additional factors such as years since first publication and sociodemographic factors is needed to determine the full impact of personal attributes on publication outcomes.

Open science practices

Article metadata used to complete this study was obtained from OpenAlex (<https://openalex.org>) and is freely available under a Creative Commons CC0 license. Processed data will be made available on Zenodo.

Author contributions

Rebecca Marjoram: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft
Geoff Krause: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing
Philippe Mongeon: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Writing – review & editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing financial or non-financial interests.

Funding information

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

References

- Archambault, É., Beaulac, O. H., & Caruso, J. (2011). Towards a multilingual, comprehensive and open scientific journal ontology. 1, 66–77. Scopus.
- Bothner, M. S., Haynes, R., Lee, W., & Smith, E. B. (2010). When Do Matthew Effects Occur? *The Journal of Mathematical Sociology*, 34(2), 80–114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222500903310960>
- CiteScore Journal Metric. Scopus. (2023, June 7). https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/30562/supporthub/scopus/
- Kim, J. W., & King, B. G. (2014). Seeing Stars: Matthew Effects and Status Bias in Major League Baseball Umpiring: *Management Science*. *Management Science*, 60(11), 2619–2644. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2014.1967>
- Larivière, V., Ni, C., Gingras, Y., Cronin, B., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2013). Bibliometrics: Global gender disparities in science. *Nature*, 504(7479), Article 7479. <https://doi.org/10.1038/504211a>
- Merton, R. K. (1968). The Matthew Effect in Science. *Science*, 159(3810), 56–63.
- Nielsen, M. W., & Andersen, J. P. (2021). Global citation inequality is on the rise. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(7), e2012208118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2012208118>
- Piezunka, H., Lee, W., Haynes, R., & Bothner, M. S. (2018). The Matthew Effect as an Unjust Competitive Advantage: Implications for Competition Near Status Boundaries. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 27(4), 378–381. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1056492617737712>
- Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts (arXiv:2205.01833). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.01833>
- Rossiter, M. W. (1993). The Matthew Matilda Effect in Science. *Social Studies of Science*, 23(2), 325–341.